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YOURS DIGITALLY: PATANJALI

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ABSTRACT

This case goes about how Mr. Sharma, HOD Marketing of Patanjali Ayurveda Limited establishes the indigenous home grown brand as a major player in FMCG sector in India, he creates a model for making Patanjali famous as famous as other FMCG major like Dabur, Himalaya etc. Prior launching the products through local Kirana stores & getting franchise mode of operation, he carefully planned the marketing strategies to compete products online & offline competitors (MNCs). Mr. Sharma has a difficult and dilemmatic task of deciding on initiatives to cash in different digital platforms. Patanjali products were previously available at its centers all over India. But here he has to not only make a pan India coverage but also to explore unknown territories in abroad. Previously Baba Ramdev was the sole face of its products, but now Mr. Sharma has to rely on various ways to make the products popular by hitting the pulse of consumers through advertisements. And simultaneously he also used digital media to make the brand presence felt all over the world. The following case gives an insight into the benefits of digital presence of branding & articulate planning of advertising.

Objectives:

1. Understand Patanjali Ayurveda Limited and its FMCG products
2. Know the brand architecture of Patanjali Ayurveda
3. Identify the mode of operation for Patanjali products.
4. Know the advertising methods of Patanjali products
5. Analyse the association of Patanjali Products with the “Make in India” movement.

Key Words: Patanjali, FMCG, Digital Media

Introduction

There are many articles written already about Baba Ramdev and Patanjali Ayurveda in the Indian business newspapers and magazines. Also a lot of research has gone into his business operation, distribution, pricing, high margins, low advertising expenditures. And even more has been written about how the company is going to jump from over Rs 2000 crores turnover to Rs 5000-6000 crores turnover in 2016. By this humongous amount it catches every body's fantasy that how it goes with such kind of high numbers so quickly. Comparative low cost, effective supply chain & economies of scale are vital cogs in this endeavor.

Here, the multiplicity of brands in Baba Ramdev's portfolio should be addressed and how they could pose a significant threat to the indigenous brands like Dabur and Himalaya. First of all there are 2 companies registered under Patanjali Ayurved.

1. Patanjali Ayurved Limited with CIN U24237DL2006PLC144789 and Registration no 144789 which has an authorized capital of Rs 500 million. This company is registered in New Delhi and is obviously the consumer facing part of the Patanjali Group.
2. Patanjali Ayurved Private Limited which is registered as a Indian non-government company with CIN U52311KL1995PTC009012 and Registration no 9012 with an authorized capital of Rs 1 million. This company is registered in Ernakulum, and no doubt is the Ayurvedic B2B arm of the Patanjali Group.

An NGO has obvious benefits since under the Income Tax Act NGO tax exemption and tax benefits are available to Donors for the donation made to a NGO through 12A, 80 g, 80GGA, 35 ac (i & ii), (i & iii), 80CCC, 80U, 35 ac, 115A, 115AB, 115AC, 115AD, and 115D for charitable purposes.

Baba Ramdev's Brand Architecture

Baba Ramdev's seat of the pants approach to branding may have something more than is immediately obvious. Now let's go through this carefully. First of all look at the double barreled name which is constructed so beautifully.

Fig.1: Brand Architecture of Baba Ramdev's Medicines

PATANJALI and AYURVEDA

Baba Ramdev owns Patanjali because of his yogic powers. (The Yoga formulae are one of the most important texts in the age-old Yoga philosophy written by the Sage Patanjali. Baba Ramdev has already gained recognition as one of its most respected modern proponents. And Acharya Balkrishna owns Ayurveda since he is an Acharya (preceptor and teacher). Yogi on the left and Acharya on the right is a really awesome combination that should win the hearts of the Indians. Two powerful forces coming together. Then on top is Swami Baba Ramdev Medicines which for some reason none of the business publications seem to have talked about but it has an important role.

Swami Baba Ramdev Medicines could be

a) What Vichy Labs is to L'Oreal?

Maybe a lesser known fact amongst consumers, but Vichy is the pharmacy brand from L'Oreal which markets serious expensive molecules in the same areas as L'Oreal in skincare and hair-care. Once the Vichy molecule has gone through its product lifecycle as a breakthrough scientific molecule it can be passed on to L'Oreal for mass markets in skin care and hair-care.

Fig.2: Swami Baba Ramdev Medicines

Much the same can happen with Swami Baba Ramdev Medicines and Patanjali Ayurveda. The breakthrough molecules from the medicine brand based on Yogic Formulae can be brought to the more popular brand. So Swami Baba Ramdev Medicines is into serious health care for a variety of chronic ailments. The website has plethora of Ayurveda medicines for every possible ailment. And they are prepared for the future and already international. Because all the prices are in \$ (USD) and the products can be bought online. This move is so smart that it competes with the major players effectively.

b) Ponds Institute is for Unilever

Except that the Ponds Institute seemed more like a hypothetical advertising property, or at best a skin and hair testing center in a Pilipino Posh mall, rather than a real manufacturing or R & D facility. It is more filmy and clearly a part of fiction. But the way the Ponds Institute was used in advertising gave it a status much above its actual existence. In the case of Baba Ramdev it is a real facility equipped lab with a proper range of Ayurveda products. Medicines therefore can lend functional credibility and product efficacy to the entire brand.

Difference between .net & .org of Patanjali

1. www.patanjali.net

2. Fig.3: Pic of .net of Patanjali

.net is their main e-commerce website. The entire range is on display here and can be bought online. People may laugh it off, but need to remember that none of our so called MNCs actually sell their products online in spite of their media comments about how they are embracing digital, which of course is more stylish than real these days. Here Patanjali scores over the MNCs.

Fig.4: Pic of .org of Patanjali

2 .org

Now .org is almost their corporate website. This is where they get into what they are about, the mission and philosophy and of course inviting dealerships. Most of it has been written very amateurish manner.

But, the dealership form available on the website is both humorous and entertaining.

The interesting part is that the form asks the dealer to **pledge allegiance to the movement.**

Notice the key words '**I am a well-wisher and supporter of this movement and is committed to get rid of MNC's loot to make the country self-reliant and economic super power**'.

Patanjali Ayurved: Advertisement Analysis

It was time to analyse their advertising and brand communication. There are 2 distinct sets of commercials for Patanjali Ayurved. One set which was produced over a year ago, which is of relatively poor quality, and another new set of commercials that were loaded on YouTube during Nov 2015 and after.

Bharat Swabhiman

The underlying subliminal theme is Bharat Swabhiman. If while watching the Patanjali Ayurved commercials one thinks it is only a logo that appears on the upper right hand corner, then it is wrong. **In fact Bharat Swabhiman is both a website and a movement.** It is riding high on the wave created by MAKE IN INDIA movement. The branding is like STAR Network or Colors or BCCI TV. It wants to carve a niche for it in customer's mind.

Fig.5: Pic of Bharat Swabhiman Web page

While speaking to consumers, what emerges is that people are genuinely happy to support a home grown Indian venture that capitalizes on two ancient Indian traditions: Ayurveda and yoga. Partly because no one has done it before. Bharat Swabhiman awakens that raw nerve in the Indian sentiment, where Indians feel that multinationals have been exploiting the Indian population. In this context Patanjali Ayurved appears like a savior to the Indian population.

Patanjali Dant Kanti Ad

The toothpaste category is one of the most difficult categories in India for new brands to enter and succeed. The spirit of Bharat Swabhiman is best represented in the Patanjali Dant Kanti commercial below. By showing an ordinary man picking up a random white coat (in the name of dental doctor or association), the commercial exposes the fake strategy of the multinationals who use white coats to lend credence to their product. This includes Colgate, Hindustan Unilever, and Sensodyne who have relied on white coats for the last few decades to lend substance to their advertising. In fact, Patanjali Ayurved represents a revival of Bharat Swabhiman. The protagonist in this commercial of Patanjali **Dant Kanti Ad** says '*Safed coat pehen kar, safed jhoot bhi bol sakta hai*' (you can wear a white coat and tell white lies). In a lighter note it shows the '*Safed Jhoot*' (*White Lies*) Earlier in the commercial the protagonist says '*Is it so difficult to recognize the truth?* Do I need to wear a white coat for you to believe me?' He then throws away a red colored toothpaste tube away. This could be either Colgate or Hindustan Unilever, red being a pre-dominant colour in several brands of toothpastes.

Patanjali Cow Ghee Ad

The second commercial that struck the cord with that of with mass is the Patanjali Cow Ghee ad. This again is another superbly placed ad. The cow being the holy revered animal of the Hindus, cow ghee naturally has much more emotional value than say for example buffalo ghee. Not many Indian consumers think of this consciously but most people in India drink buffalo milk. This is the basis on which Patanjali dairy revolution is based. Operation White Flood (White Revolution) was about buffalo milk. Dr. V. Kurien's major contribution was really adapting dairy technology to buffaloes in India since all dairy technology overseas was built on cow's milk. In very real terms there is little difference between cow's milk and buffalo milk in nutritional values. If anything buffalo milk might just have some more minerals than cow's milk. But coming back to the matter of cow ghee. Cow Ghee would tug

at the Indian heart more than anything else. **The whole emergence of *Vanaspati* in this country was based on the price of ghee becoming unaffordable.** People shifted because they couldn't afford ghee. In fact, ghee also became the benchmark for Vanaspati to compare itself. Now Ghee is an important part of the Patanjali Ayurved portfolio and contributes to Rs 1200 crores out of the estimated Rs 2500 crores of sale turnover being touted in media, or in other words almost half their turnover. The commercial uses all the symbols of success that is known to have worked for Ghee advertising and later for Vanaspati advertising (Remember Dalda).

Shudh ghee (pure ghee), Dadi Ma (grandmother), Sushil Kumar as a famous Indian wrestler is most appropriate because of the traditional Indian belief that 'Ghee makes you strong'. Here the conscious decision is to attach the advertisement to the Indianised thought process. The commercial then signs off with '**The Strength of Champions**' (Champion ban ne ki Takaat). The success of Cow Ghee brand is commendable. And one can be sure this is not just a flash of lightning! To conclude, Patanjali Ayurved seems to be pressing all the right buttons to appeal to the Indian public. We are sure to see more advertising in the near future that embodies the spirit of Bharat Swabhiman, and attacks MNCs consciously and large Indian companies in the Indian market.

New Innovative labelling of Patanjali Products; Back of Pack (BOP) is the New Front of Pack (FOP)

Source of Credibility:

Nivea's Blue Pack (Dabba), Surf 's light blue color, Dove's 1/4th moisturizing cream or Ponds' white pack are at the heart of the belief & trust around these products. These brands hence do stand for CARE & TRUST. These can be called **temple ingredients or products**, which give an reliable atmosphere not just to a particular product but to the entire product category. These are temple ingredients / products which give back to the entire portfolio of products umbrella under the mother brand. Temple ingredients are the driving key ingredients which pull the customers. And **temple product** is the main product that carries temple ingredients. Patanjali has a vastly different source. A source which comes from **spirituality/divinity & health**. Unlike commercial brands, Patanjali's source credibility was beamed into consumers' hearts & minds early in the mornings via television sets through Astha & Prathna channels which popularize '*Olulomvilom*' and '*Kapalvati*' like anything.

Baba Ramdev garnered great amount of trust and ownership for spiritual & physical well-being. Propagated yoga, with him & his body being the most visible proof point for the success of this approach. While preaching *pranayama*, humans being made with "*prakriti*" / nature was strongly embedded into consumers' minds and dialed-up age old beliefs around Ayurvedic & natural which were still prevalent today. Brand Ramdev hence stood for more than just spirituality, he also stood for body (read health) benefits of Ayurveda. Hence brand Patanjali has a source credibility which is unbeatable, unmatched & unprecedented.

Triggers for mass acceptance & appreciation:

India is seeing a contrasting trend while it comes to packaged foods. At the bottom of the pyramid packaged goods represent safety & hygiene. So many categories are still under penetrated, that efforts for conversion from loose/unpackaged is still on (example: Soya Bean and chips brands at the rural level are casting doubts over the taste, safety & hygiene of loose soya & chips, promising the safety in packaged at the factory and preserved), while in the middle & the top of the pyramid there are strong trends of negative or no trust towards packaged goods. Packaged goods are being seen as full of chemicals, not being hygienically packed and lack of honesty & transparency in claims (from manufacturing to delivery to shelf). Socio-culturally, the brand controversies around Colas & Chocolates, to the latest noodles is further augmenting these fears. Primarily around food & beverage and personal care these fears are heightened. While on the other hand lifestyle diseases are plaguing India, with India slated to become the Diabetes capital of the world soon. Hence pro-active healthcare products from *Chyavanprash* to *amla murabbas* etc; are also on the rise. Aloe Vera products, Basil & Ginger concoctions are being recommended by doctors for hyper acidity & various other ailments. This is further raising consumer consciousness about natural based proactive health care. The Facebook timelines being flooded by sponsored posts & shares from friends featuring tips to live naturally and organically. Living Traditionally & Organic India are few of the many such pages recommending natural remedies and also casting aspirations on commercial brands. Social Media has also been the loud speaker raising fears & casting aspirations on commercially packaged goods. Whether it is the anti-shampoo movement "no-poo" movement in the west, "return to naturals movements" like coconut oil based products as being good for health movements based out of Australia or anti-bottled water movement in the US, social media brings these news right to door step.

So "consciousness of consumption" is on the rise at all strata of the Indian society & a strong foot print of Patanjali products are seen primarily in these categories of pro-active health

care, OTC(Over The Counter) remedies, Food & beverage categories and personal care. Brand Patanjali is very strategically putting place other brand pillars. Though they leverage Ramdev, they also have an Ayurvedic institute & a health care committee which are slowly but surely being built into the narrative. They are counter to the P&G and Unilever's labs. Strategically beyond a single person, these institutes are faceless and hence can sustain the brand even through any damage to Baba Ramdev's credibility. It is also seen "movement marketing" in its brand craft. "*Swasth yevam samruddh bharat abhiyaan*".

The movement for a healthy & hence prosperous India is also being communicated with every particular TV Commercial & communication piece. Every movement has ambassadors and all the Ramdev foot soldiers not only adopt. But also advocate these products and so do many others who have used these products and are convinced. The "healthy & prosperous India" movement is a great activation platform with amazing consumer engagement possibilities. This movement is well crafted with better semiotics can actually cut through all levels, because beyond the 'Swadeshi' movement and political associations, Patanjali is managing to craft into its brand core imagery of Ayurvedic/Natural/Pro-active". These will stand the test of time, as long as the brand slowly starts operating as a stand-alone. Baba Ramdev is the apt stimulus for the first phase of the launch of this brand. It has managed to make the brand defy gravity, however for it to reach orbit and sustain itself...slowly but surely there is a stand-alone nature that needs to be crafted in.

While the Baba will continue to keep adding into the brand's popularity and penetration from the outside, the brand can already be seen leaning on the other pillars (the *Divya Yog Mandir Trust and Patanjali Yog Peeth*) being created for it. There are great stories of specially grown endangered herbs, care of manufacturing in ensuring that "from the grass to the glass" products are safe etc; which can be taken to main stream media and popularized which will see the brand get more robust cut-through & conversion even amongst the higher level. Possibly another range which is a little more sophisticated in its semiotics but without losing the humility, approachability and earthiness of the mother brand could actually make this a brand capable of straddling all levels' with different ranges and different product portfolios. Undercutting other brands on pricing speaks for itself and does not need to be elaborated upon. Last but not the least worthy of mention is the brand's distribution strategy. While they have gone e-tail and hence opened up a whole lot of consumer households, with this move they are also acquiring a few hues of suitable-modernity and "with the times".

While the distributors/retailers the brand is also getting are not just any commercial retailers. They are *bhakt*s and *converts* to this way of living. Hence unlike any other brands retailer/distributor advocacy for the brand is very high and from the core. Many a major brands would die for this kind of a pull. Again this comes from such a poignant source credibility. This brand can also be seen making strong ventures into modern retail and hence leaving no retail channel untouched.

The one last thing which should be mentioned is CSR. This brand has managed to uniquely link its CSR initiative with retail. Small Patanjali stores being run by the differently abled and the poor. Like Lions club used to sponsor STD booths to small Kirana stores for the under privileged, Patanjali is also doing the same. This adds immense goodwill to the brand.

This following social media share best warns Patanjali of not being in a rush and hence getting their product ingredient stories right. Should Patanjali rather than not enter some product categories, if it cannot manage to provide natural is a question that must act as a filter for variants and product categories selection. For Patanjali is the brand which has made BOP (Back of Pack) into the FOP (Front of Pack) in mainstream FMCG categories.

Conclusion

Baba Ramdev's brand seems well configured and ready for takeoff. It seems to have all the magic ingredients of success.

1. The brand has moved into e-commerce besides being available with retail chains and under its own distribution centers.
2. The Ramdev Medicines brand is ready for export with foreign exchange earning potential and could be a great success if marketed successfully given the weakness that the West has for both Yoga and Herbal alternatives.
3. The brand pyramid has legs. Products are available online and through offline retail.
4. And finally it's not only his companies that are digital. Baba Ramdev is himself digital. He has 541k followers on Twitter. Big MNC CEO's are going to find it difficult to match this kind of popularity in the near future. On Facebook Baba Ramdev has 5.7 million people liking his page. (Even Facebook could get only 11 million consumers to vote for Free Basics!)
5. And with the development of 'Make in India' movement in full swing Patanjali will certainly go to another level due to its '*Swadeshi*' movement. Baba Ramdev's sutras

in the business world may well have a twist that the MNCs and large Indian firms may find hard to emulate & explain.

Resources:

1. Prabhakar Mundkur's blog on brand management of Patanjali Ayurved Products in Advertising Age & www.marketingbuzzar.com
2. Kalyan Challapali Ram's blog on new packaging techniques of Patanjali Products in www.linkedin.com
3. www.patanjaliayurved.net
4. www.patanjaliayurved.org